

INTERPRETATION OF VIEWS ABOUT THE CONCEPT OF LANGUAGE AND SPEECH

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Abstract. *Formation and development of the skill of using linguistic units in our speech. Formation the ability of to allocate language units and speech units.*

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Introduction. In our Republic, which is considered as fast developing country, like all the other areas a large-scale work is being done in the field of linguistics. Due to the fact that socio-political, economic and cultural changes in society are expressed primarily in language, the struggle for control over the literary language, its purity and culture has always gained actuality. In recent years, in Uzbek linguistics a particular attention has been paid to deep and comprehensive scientific studies of culture and manner of speech, literary language and its norms. The formation history of uzbek speech culture and development issues and based on that to show the uniqueness of the Uzbek national mentality in the world linguistic landscape is one of the urgent tasks of linguistics at present time.

As the President of Uzbekistan suggested: "The Uzbek language, one of the oldest and richest languages in the world, is a symbol of our national identity and independent country, that appreciates a spiritual wealth and significant attention to our people. Anyone who wants to feel the rich grace, charm and power of the Uzbek language, its limitless possibilities, should listen to the legends of our mothers, our thousand-year-old epics, our immortal statuses, listen to magical songs, our bakhshis and hafizs. The history of the Uzbek language, which belongs to the large family of Turkic languages is closely connected with the centuries-old past of our people, their dreams and sorrows, triumphs and victories. In Uzbek linguistics, ancient Turkish monuments and the works of great scientists, especially Alisher Navoi, Yusuf Khos Khajib, Akhmad Yungnaki, Kaykovus, Farabi, Makhmud Koshgari, which are important in the development of the Uzbek language are studied in different important aspects. The study of the historical roots of Uzbek speech culture, aspects of its formation serves to identify the specific features of the speech of native speakers of the Uzbek language, which has been formed since ancient times.

Language and speech are closely related phenomena. Language is the material component for speech, speech is formed on the basis of this component. Everything in a language is common to the linguistic community. Language contains spiritual and material components, and the word is the mental component in people's memory; the material component is word forms, morphemes and sounds used in the process of creating speech. The fact that language is a mental phenomenon lies in its preservation in consciousness, while its material phenomenon is determined by the means of language.

Speech is the process of using a unique tool called language, which performs very important tasks and manifestates the capabilities of linguistic units in relation to such phenomena as existence, thinking, consciousness and situation. Speech is a language in motion, it arises in the

process of movement of the speech organs and consists of word forms, phrases and sentences. The concept of speech culture, the desire to speak culturally, is a long-standing phenomenon in all national languages. This concept is associated with certain linguistic norms, ethical and aesthetic requirements.

Literary analysis and methodology

Since ancient times, many linguists have interpreted the concepts of language and speech as distinct from each other. They will be illustrated below with examples. Navoi considers the power of the word infinite and explains it as follows.

Olibmen taxti farmoning‘a oson,
Cherik tortmay Xitoydan to Xuroson.

Navoi interprets language and speech as phenomena that cannot exist isolately. Language is an object, the possibility of speech, the speech is reality, that assumes the organization of speech on the basis of linguistic component. The proof of this statement can be seen below. Language is an instrument of speech that has its own significance. If speech turns out to be inappropriate, it is a disaster of language. Yugnakiy also left very relevant thoughts regarding this issue. They also commented on the purposeful use of language and explained it as follows, arguing about the consequences of using every word in a language without thinking.

Tiling bakta tutg‘il , tishing sinmasun,
Qoli chiqsa bakta tishingni siyur.
Sonip so‘zlagan er so‘zi so‘z sog‘i,
O‘kush yangshagan tile y olmas yog‘i.

Similar ideas related to language and speech can be observed in Koshgari's works. Koshgari paid attention to the word, which is the basic unit of language and speech and settled as a lexicologist, seminologist and lexicographer, the meaning of a word, a characteristic of a word in its own and figurative sense. They left enough information about this in the works “Devon-u Lugotit Turk”. Koshifiy, a contemporary of Navoi, who also expressed his thoughts and comments, paying close attention to the issue of language and speech in his work “Futuvvatnomayi Sultani”. This is the way how they expressed these ideas. “If they ask whether this is your word or you are the word, say: I am the word, and the word is mine. Since the word is the fruit of the human tree, neither the fruit can be separated from the tree, nor the tree from the fruit. They compare a word to a child and a good word is called a good child, and an unsuitable word is compared to an inept child. There are many such examples. However, the main and actual criterion of linguistics and systematic linguistics of the 20th century was the distinction between language and speech relations, linguistic and speech phenomena and units. If we turn to the history of this problem, then, according to Professor Kh. Nematov, the difference between language and speech phenomena can be seen in the methods of studying the language of Arabic linguistics, which were formed in the 7th-9th centuries. The problem of language and speech - *energeo* (movement, process, force) and *ergon* (work) in the language of Wilhelm von Humboldt, the founder of general theoretical linguistics, G. Steinthal, the founder of psychologism in linguistics, “stable essence” and “Driving forces” in language, great theorist and practical linguist Baudouin, are also given in the teachings of de Courtenay about the stability and change of language. It should be noted that the dialectical relationship between language and speech found its first real, perfect scientific and theoretical solution in the works of the great linguist Ferdinand de Saussure, who made a sharp turn in linguistics.

Therefore, the question of language and speech has been and will remain a serious theoretical problem not only of systematic linguistics, but also of world linguistics in all periods - both diachronic and synchronic. Because without this extremely complex and urgent problem of linguistics, it is impossible to fully, completely and objectively solve a number of the most important and fundamental issues not only of theoretical general linguistics, but also of specific practical linguistics. Accordingly, language and speech, dialectics remain one of the constant problems of world linguistics. F. de Saussure's definition of language and speech as means of communication and expression of the people, their differentiation from each other caused a conflict of opinions among scientists. "There is one thing, language and speech are considered one thing," and a number of other scientists expressed the opinion that it is necessary to distinguish between language and speech, that they are different. So, at present, the distinction between language and speech, events and units have taken a strong place both in general linguistics and in Uzbek linguistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The relationship between language and speech is also known from the following. Language is organized on the basis of speech, which is realized through speech. Language is the basis and the product of speech as well. If language is the component for communication, then speech is the formation of ideas from this component. As F. de Saussure said, language is necessary for speech to be understandable to us, and speech is necessary for the development, survival and formation of language. From a historical perspective, facts precede language.

The survival, existence and development of language is carried out through speech. For example, when people use Uzbek language in their speech, it means the existence of the Uzbek language and its usage. Or if people use English in my speech, it means that this language exists and that this language is alive. So, every obvious manifestation of language is real speech and speech activity.

Language is a means of communication, speech is a way of communication. Language is a way of expressing possibility, speech, reality, impact. Language is universality, speech is particularity and individuality. According to the origin of speech, it is primary, that before the appearance of speech, speech sounds appeared and language is secondary, formed and developed on the basis of speech. Language is learned through analysis, and speech through perception and understanding. The life of a language is long, which is connected with the life of the people and the life of speech is short, as it exists only at the moment of speech. This can be expressed in table in the following way.

Linguistic unit	Speech unit	Language	Speech
Phoneme	Phone	General	Privacy
Morpheme	Morph	Possibility	Reality
Lexeme	Lexis	Readiness	Performance
Construction	Form of the word; word combination; speech; microtext, macrotex	Limitation	Limitless

Above there was expressed the conclusion arising from reflections on language and speech in the form of a table.

CONCLUSION

Summarizing it can be suggested that the concept of language and speech are two concepts that cannot exist without each other. From one side, when a language becomes a dead language, when people do not use it in their speech, the existence of the language lies in the existence of speech. From the other side, the possibilities of language are limitless, everyone uses it depending on their intellectual, spiritual, social, economic and even general level of acquired knowledge. In short, judicious use of language is a virtue of a wise and smart person. It is true that Uzbek is a language with great potential. If people can show that this language is not inferior to the languages of world countries, it will prove that this language has significant possibilities. Good results can be achieved if it will be taught the ways of how to write a beautiful speech using the standards of the literary language of specialists working in all languages. That is why at present time a speech and communication, the ability to freely convey one's opinion to others, have been brought to the level of public policy. This is reflected in the programs of the Ministry of Education and Culture.

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